

Supplementary Material

2 I. UNCERTAINTY ANALYSIS

3 The uncertainties in both instantaneous PIV velocity fields and mean flow parameters
 4 were evaluated to quantify the associated measurement errors. For all variables, the precision
 5 uncertainty, \mathcal{U}_P , was computed directly from the data. When applicable, bias uncertainties,
 6 \mathcal{U}_B , were also considered, based on either manufacturer specifications or independent cali-
 7 bration. Following the ISO guidelines, the precision uncertainty of a variable ϕ with a 95%
 8 confidence interval and $N_t \geq 30$ samples is given by:

$$\mathcal{U}_{P,\phi} = \frac{1.96 \sigma_\phi}{\sqrt{N_t}},$$

9 where σ_ϕ is the standard deviation of ϕ . For small sample sizes ($N_t = 3$), the expression
 10 becomes:

$$\mathcal{U}_{P,\phi} = \frac{4.303 \sigma_\phi}{\sqrt{N_t}}.$$

11 For a derived quantity F that is a function of M independent variables, $F(\phi_1, \phi_2, \dots, \phi_M)$,
 12 the combined uncertainty is estimated using the standard error propagation formula:

$$\mathcal{U}_F^2 = \sum_{i=1}^M \left(\frac{\partial F}{\partial \phi_i} \right)^2 \mathcal{U}_{\phi_i}^2, \quad (1)$$

13 valid for small, random, and uncorrelated errors.

14 A. Instantaneous velocity fields

15 An instantaneous wall-parallel PIV velocity component at a point in the flow field is
 16 defined as

$$U_s = \frac{\Delta s}{\Delta t} = \frac{\Delta S}{M \Delta t_{\text{PIV}}},$$

17 where Δs and ΔS are the particle displacements in the physical and image coordinates,
 18 respectively, M is the optical magnification, and Δt_{PIV} is the time interval between two
 19 consecutive PIV frames.

20 The bias uncertainty of U_s can be estimated by propagating the bias uncertainties of its
 21 independent variables using equation 1, as given by Adrian and Westerweel [1]:

$$\left(\frac{\mathcal{U}_{B,U_s}}{U_s} \right)^2 = \left(\frac{\mathcal{U}_{B,\Delta S}}{\Delta S} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\mathcal{U}_{B,\Delta t_{\text{PIV}}}}{\Delta t_{\text{PIV}}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\mathcal{U}_{B,M}}{M} \right)^2. \quad (2)$$

22 Here, $\mathcal{U}_{B,\Delta S} \approx 0.1 D_p$, where D_p is the mean particle image diameter. In this study,
 23 $D_p = 2.86$ pixels, the magnification factor was $M = 3.4$, and the time delay between frames
 24 for the water flow measurements was $\Delta t_{\text{PIV}} = 40\text{--}60 \mu\text{s}$. The r.m.s. error of the third-
 25 order polynomial image-to-world calibration mapping was adopted as the bias uncertainty
 26 of magnification, yielding $\mathcal{U}_{B,M} = 0.13$.

27 The bias uncertainty in timing was taken as the rise/fall time of the illumination source,
 28 reported as $\mathcal{U}_{B,\Delta t_{\text{PIV}}} = 0.5 \mu\text{s}$ by the manufacturer (iLA.LPS v3; ILA 5150 GmbH). The
 29 maximum bias uncertainty in velocity estimation arises from the minimum values of Δt_{PIV}
 30 and ΔS , which in the present measurements were $\Delta t_{\text{PIV},\text{min}} = 40 \mu\text{s}$ and $\Delta S_{\text{min}} \approx 5.1$ pixels.

31 Using equation 1, the relative contributions of each source to the maximum bias uncer-
 32 tainty in U_s are

$$\left(\frac{\mathcal{U}_{B,\Delta S}}{\Delta S}\right)_{\text{max}} \times 100\% \approx 5.6\%, \quad (3)$$

$$\left(\frac{\mathcal{U}_{B,\Delta t_{\text{PIV}}}}{\Delta t_{\text{PIV}}}\right)_{\text{max}} \times 100\% \approx 1.3\%, \quad (4)$$

$$\left(\frac{\mathcal{U}_{B,M}}{M}\right)_{\text{max}} \times 100\% \approx 3.8\%, \quad (5)$$

35 which together yield a maximum total relative bias uncertainty in U_s of

$$\left(\frac{\mathcal{U}_{B,U_s}}{U_s}\right)_{\text{max}} \times 100\% \approx 6.9\%. \quad (6)$$

36 The results indicate that, under the tested flow conditions, the relative contributions to
 37 the maximum bias uncertainty in the instantaneous U_s velocity arise predominantly from
 38 particle displacement, followed by magnification (calibration), and then timing. Accordingly,
 39 the combined influence of these components yields a maximum relative bias uncertainty of
 40 approximately 7% in the wall-parallel velocity measurements.

41 The precision (random) uncertainties associated with the instantaneous velocity fields
 42 were evaluated using the correlation statistics method proposed by Wieneke [2], as imple-
 43 mented in the commercial software DaVis V8.4 (LaVision GmbH). This method estimates
 44 local uncertainty by analysing the correlation plane resulting from each image pair, taking
 45 into account the spatial distribution of particle image intensities. For each flow condition,
 46 the instantaneous uncertainty fields in the wall-parallel and wall-normal directions, denoted

47 by $\mathcal{U}_{U_s}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ and $\mathcal{U}_{U_n}(\mathbf{x}, t)$, were ensemble-averaged over $N_t \approx 11\,000$ samples, assuming
 48 statistical stationarity of the flow.

49 The resulting ensemble-averaged uncertainty fields, $\langle \mathcal{U}_{U_s} \rangle(\mathbf{x})$ and $\langle \mathcal{U}_{U_n} \rangle(\mathbf{x})$, were further
 50 averaged along the wall-parallel coordinate s for the fully developed channel flows, under the
 51 assumption of streamwise homogeneity. The final wall-normal uncertainty profiles, $\overline{\langle \mathcal{U}_{U_s} \rangle}(n)$
 52 and $\overline{\langle \mathcal{U}_{U_n} \rangle}(n)$, were normalised by the corresponding mean velocity magnitudes (reported in
 53 table II in the main manuscript) and are presented in figure 1(a,b) for the water flow.

Figure 1. Wall-normal variations of the ensemble and spatially averaged instantaneous uncertainties of the (a) wall-parallel and (b) wall-normal velocity fields relative to their mean velocities, U_b (see table II in the main manuscript). The instantaneous uncertainties were obtained using the correlation statistics method [2].

54 As shown in figure 1(a), the wall-normal distribution of the spatially averaged uncertainty
 55 in the wall-parallel velocity component, $\overline{\langle \mathcal{U}_{U_s} \rangle}$, is highest near the wall, reaching up to 4.5%
 56 of the local mean velocity. Away from the wall, the uncertainty gradually decreases to values
 57 on the order of 2% of U_b . A similar trend is observed for the wall-normal velocity component,
 58 $\overline{\langle \mathcal{U}_{U_n} \rangle}$, as shown in figure 1(b). However, the magnitudes are slightly lower, with a near-wall
 59 maximum of approximately 3% of U_b and a minimum of around 1.5% farther from the wall.

60 Figure 2 presents the temporal evolution of the spatially averaged wall-parallel velocity
 61 uncertainty, $\overline{\overline{\mathcal{U}_{U_s}}}$, for the C-FPG water flow case at $Re_\tau = 286$. The uncertainty values are
 62 normalised by the corresponding mean wall-parallel velocity. Here, N denotes the image
 63 pair index, and $N_t \approx 11\,000$ is the total number of PIV realisations. The time series exhibits
 64 statistically stationary behaviour, with instantaneous uncertainty fluctuating between ap-

65 proximately $0.015 U_b$ and $0.030 U_b$. The mean value is $\langle \overline{\overline{U}}_{U_s} \rangle = 0.020 U_b$, and the standard
 66 deviation is $\sigma_{\overline{\overline{U}}_{U_s}} = 0.0023 U_b$. Although not shown, the wall-normal velocity uncertainties
 67 exhibit a similar level of temporal consistency, with $\langle \overline{\overline{U}}_{U_n} \rangle = 0.018 U_b$ and $\sigma_{\overline{\overline{U}}_{U_n}} = 0.0021 U_b$.

Figure 2. Percentage of the temporal changes of the instantaneous wall-parallel uncertainty for fully-developed water flow with $Re_\tau = 286$ (see table II in the main manuscript) relative to its mean velocity, $U_b = 1.1 \text{ ms}^{-1}$, spatially averaged over the area covered by the interrogated FOV. Here, $N_t \approx 11\,000$.

68 B. Mean fields

69 The precision uncertainty of the mean wall-parallel velocity, $\langle U_s \rangle$, is estimated as $\mathcal{U}_{P, \langle U_s \rangle} =$
 70 $\sigma_{u_s} / \sqrt{N_t}$ [3, 4], where σ_{u_s} is the standard deviation of the instantaneous U_s velocity from
 71 N_t samples. The corresponding uncertainty in the mean Reynolds shear stress is given by

$$\mathcal{U}_{P, \langle u_s u_n \rangle} = \frac{\sigma_{u_s} \sigma_{u_n}}{\sqrt{(1 + r_{sn}^2)/(N_t - 1)}},$$

72 where r_{sn} is the sample correlation coefficient between u_s and u_n fields [4]. For the Reynolds
 73 normal stresses, the uncertainties follow $\mathcal{U}_{P, \langle u_i^2 \rangle} = \langle u_i^2 \rangle \sqrt{2/N_t}$, where $i = s, n$.

74 Figure 3(a–d) illustrates the wall-normal variations of the spatially averaged normalised
 75 uncertainties of the mean velocity and Reynolds stress components. As shown in figure 3(a),
 76 the uncertainty in $\langle U_s \rangle$ remains below 0.2% of U_b and decreases slightly farther from the
 77 wall. This trend is consistent across all three tested water flow conditions.

78 The relative uncertainty in the Reynolds shear stress, shown in figure 3(b), is largest near
 79 the wall and at positions close to the channel centreline, reaching up to 7% and 10% of the
 80 local $-\langle u_s u_n \rangle$, respectively. These values gradually reduce to 2–3% in regions away from
 81 the wall and the centreline.

82 Figure 3(c) shows the uncertainty in the wall-parallel Reynolds normal stress, $\overline{\langle u_s^2 \rangle}$. The
 83 lowest uncertainty, approximately 1.1%, is observed near the wall, and it increases gradually
 84 to $\mathcal{O}(1.3\%)$ farther away. A slight increase near the channel centre does not exceed 1.3% of
 85 the local stress magnitude.

86 The uncertainties in the wall-normal Reynolds stress, $\overline{\langle u_n^2 \rangle}$, shown in figure 3(d), also
 87 peak near the wall at $\approx 1.6\%$ of the local value. These uncertainties reduce to $\mathcal{O}(1.3\%)$ in
 88 the bulk flow region, displaying a similar trend to the wall-parallel counterpart.

Figure 3. Wall-normal percentage variation of the spatially averaged normalized uncertainties of the mean (a) wall-parallel velocity, (b) Reynolds shear stress, (c) wall-parallel, and (d) wall-normal Reynolds stresses.

89 C. Scaling parameters

90 The uncertainty associated with the mean wall shear stress, \mathcal{U}_{τ_w} , was estimated by prop-
 91 agating the uncertainties of the wall shear viscosity, \mathcal{U}_{μ_w} , and the mean wall shear strain

Table I. Estimated relative percentage of the mean uncertainties of the scaling parameters.

C_s (p.p.m.)	Pure water	200	400
$(\mathcal{U}_{\mu_w}/\mu_w) \times 100\%$	8.4	2.4	2.5
$(\mathcal{U}_{\tau_w}/\tau_w) \times 100\%$	8.4	2.4	2.5
$(\mathcal{U}_{u_\tau}/u_\tau) \times 100\%$	4.2	1.2	1.3
$(\mathcal{U}_{\lambda_v}/\lambda_v) \times 100\%$	9.4	2.7	2.8
$[\mathcal{U}_{n/\lambda_v}/(n/\lambda_v)] \times 100\%$	9.4	2.7	2.8

92 rate, $\mathcal{U}_{\dot{\gamma}_w}$, using the standard error propagation relation:

$$\left(\frac{\mathcal{U}_{\tau_w}}{\tau_w}\right)^2 = \left(\frac{\mathcal{U}_{\mu_w}}{\mu_w}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\mathcal{U}_{\dot{\gamma}_w}}{\dot{\gamma}_w}\right)^2. \quad (7)$$

93 No specific information was available from the manufacturer to directly estimate the bias
 94 uncertainty in the shear viscosity measurements. Therefore, the precision uncertainty of the
 95 wall shear viscosity, \mathcal{U}_{μ_w} , was evaluated based on three repeated measurements ($N_t = 3$)
 96 at each shear rate, as shown in figure 3(a) of the main manuscript. For each solution,
 97 the relative uncertainties $(\mathcal{U}_{\mu_w}/\mu_w)$ were averaged across all measurement points and are
 98 reported in table I as the estimated uncertainties of wall shear viscosity in the respective
 99 solution flows.

100 The mean wall shear strain rate, $\dot{\gamma}_w$, was determined by fitting a linear profile to the mean
 101 velocity data within the viscous sublayer. Analysis of the fitted lines indicated a maximum
 102 root-mean-square (r.m.s.) fitting error of approximately 0.011 s^{-1} . This error was adopted
 103 as the uncertainty in the determination of $\dot{\gamma}_w$, i.e., $\mathcal{U}_{\dot{\gamma}_w} = 0.011 \text{ s}^{-1}$. According to table II
 104 from the manuscript, the lowest measured shear strain rate in the C-FPG water flow was
 105 $\dot{\gamma}_w = 2\,250 \text{ s}^{-1}$, which corresponds to a maximum relative uncertainty of

$$\left(\frac{\mathcal{U}_{\dot{\gamma}_w}}{\dot{\gamma}_w}\right)_{\max} \times 100\% \approx 5 \times 10^{-4}\%,$$

106 a value negligible compared to the uncertainties in the wall shear viscosity, μ_w , measure-
 107 ments. As the results indicate, uncertainties in wall shear stress measurements are predom-
 108 inantly influenced by the uncertainties in viscosity, which tend to be relatively higher for
 109 water compared to PAM solutions.

110 The uncertainties in the friction velocity u_τ , the viscous length scale λ_v , and the wall-
 111 normal position n normalized by λ_v and δ were estimated via uncertainty propagation fol-

112 lowing equation 1. The fluid density was taken as $\langle \rho_L \rangle = 1000 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$, with a precision
 113 uncertainty of $\mathcal{U}_{P,\rho_L} = 0.078 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$, derived from a standard deviation $\sigma_{\rho_L} = 1.25 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$
 114 over $N_t = 1000$ flowmeter measurements (Sec. II in the main manuscript). The manu-
 115 facturer (Krohne Optimass 7000) specifies a density measurement accuracy of $\pm 0.5 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$,
 116 which was taken as the bias uncertainty \mathcal{U}_{B,ρ_L} . Consequently, the relative total uncertainty
 117 in density is

$$\left(\frac{\mathcal{U}_{\rho_L}}{\rho_L} \right) \times 100\% = 5.06 \times 10^{-4}\%.$$

118 This value is insignificant relative to \mathcal{U}_{τ_w} , implying—according to table I—that the relative
 119 uncertainty in wall shear stress is approximately twice that of the friction velocity.

120 In this study, the uncertainty in estimating the wall-normal position, n , was assumed to
 121 be equal to the image calibration error, which was approximately 0.13 pixels. The smallest
 122 resolvable wall-normal position above the wall equalled the spatial resolution in the normal
 123 direction, which was approximately 8 pixels. Accordingly, the maximum relative uncertainty
 124 in n was estimated as:

$$\left(\frac{\mathcal{U}_n}{n} \right)_{\max} \times 100\% \approx 1.63\%.$$

125 The uncertainty in determining the boundary layer thickness, δ , was assumed to arise
 126 from the combination of the uncertainties in the edge velocity, U_e , and the wall position,
 127 n_w . The uncertainty in U_e was found to be:

$$\left(\frac{\mathcal{U}_{U_e}}{U_e} \right) \times 100\% \approx 0.13\%,$$

128 as shown in figure 3(a). The uncertainty in the wall location was $\mathcal{U}_{n_w} \approx 0.85$ pixels, which
 129 corresponds to:

$$\left(\frac{\mathcal{U}_{n_w}}{\Delta n} \right) \times 100\% = 10.65\%,$$

130 where Δn is the distance from the wall to the edge of the boundary layer.

131 As a result, the uncertainty in the estimation of the boundary layer thickness was:

$$\left(\frac{\mathcal{U}_\delta}{\delta} \right) \times 100\% \approx 10.65\%,$$

132 indicating that errors in locating the wall dominate the total uncertainty in δ , while uncer-
 133 tainties in determining U_e are relatively negligible.

134 **II. VALIDATION OF THE TURBULENCE STATISTICS**

135 Figure 4 illustrates the statistical convergence of $\langle U_s \rangle$ at four wall-normal positions for
 136 the fully developed C-FPG water flow at $Re_\tau = 200$. The instantaneous mean velocity
 137 at each wall-normal location, $\langle U_s \rangle_N$, is normalised by its long-time average $\langle U_s \rangle_{N_t}$, where
 138 $N_t = 11,000$ is the total number of acquired PIV velocity fields. The results show that
 139 the mean velocities fall within the reliability margin of $\pm 2\sigma_{u_s}/\langle U_s \rangle$ [1], where σ_{u_s} is the
 140 root-mean-square of the velocity fluctuations u_s , and $\sigma_{u_s}/\langle U_s \rangle$ denotes the normalised tur-
 141 bulence intensity. In this study, a representative value of $\sigma_{u_s} \approx 0.1$ was assumed based on
 142 experimental observations.

143 To quantify the convergence quality, the random error of the mean velocity measurements
 144 was defined as the maximum relative variation in $\langle U_s \rangle_N$ within the last 20% of the samples.
 145 This metric is given by:

$$e_{R,\langle U_s \rangle} \% = \left[\left| \langle U_s \rangle_{N,\max} - \langle U_s \rangle_{N,\min} \right| / \langle U_s \rangle_{N_t} \right]_{0.8 N_t \leq N \leq N_t}. \quad (8)$$

146 This definition provides a practical measure of residual fluctuations and ensures that the
 147 final ensemble-averaged velocities are statistically reliable.

Figure 4. Variation of the ensemble-averaged wall-parallel velocity $\langle U_s \rangle$ at four different wall distances, as a function of the sample number N . The long-time average $\langle U_s \rangle_{N_t}$ normalizes the results, where $N_t = 11\,000$, is the total number of velocity fields. The dashed black lines denote the reliability margins [1]. The results correspond to the fully-developed water flow at $Re_\tau = 200$.

148 As listed in table II, the random noises of the measured $\langle U_s \rangle$ were lower than 0.5%,

Table II. Random noises of the mean wall-parallel velocity and Reynolds stresses at different wall-normal positions for the fully-developed C-FPG turbulent water flow at three different Re_τ .

Parameter	$Re_\tau = 200$			$Re_\tau = 245$			$Re_\tau = 286$		
	$n^+ = 14$	49	119	$n^+ = 17$	60	146	$n^+ = 19$	69	169
$e_{R,\langle U_s \rangle} \%$	0.42	0.44	0.35	0.49	0.49	0.38	0.47	0.43	0.41
$e_{R,\langle u_s u_n \rangle} \%$	3.95	3.63	3.50	6.85	5.81	3.52	5.37	4.29	3.33
$e_{R,\langle u_s^2 \rangle} \%$	1.17	2.56	3.44	1.68	3.51	3.91	2.67	2.82	4.57
$e_{R,\langle u_n^2 \rangle} \%$	1.51	1.26	1.30	2.17	1.94	2.37	2.83	1.70	1.61

149 showing a good statistical convergence. In the tested flow conditions, the random noises of
 150 the mean velocities were maximum near the wall and decreased for positions far from the
 151 wall.

152 Figure 5 proves that $\langle u_s \rangle$ tends to zero by the long-time averaging used in the current
 153 study. Figure 5(b-d) illustrates the statistical convergence of the Reynolds stresses, each
 154 normalized by its long-time average. As seen, the N -sample averaged Reynolds shear stress,
 155 $\langle u_s u_n \rangle_N$, shows higher fluctuations compared to other Reynolds stresses. The random noises
 156 associated with $\langle u_s u_n \rangle$, listed in table II, were overall higher than the wall-parallel and wall-
 157 normal Reynolds stresses at different wall-normal positions. With $e_R < 7\%$, the measured
 158 Reynolds stresses show good statistical convergence over the BL. The random noise decreases
 159 systematically as the probed wall-normal positions move away from the wall.

160 The statistical convergence of the mean wall-parallel velocity in tested PAM solutions was
 161 investigated by monitoring the variation of the N -sample averages, $\langle U_s \rangle_N$, at different wall
 162 distances and three different flow conditions. Figure 6 illustrates the convergence of $\langle U_s \rangle$ at
 163 four wall distances from the buffer layer to the outer layer, near the channel's centerline, for
 164 the fully-developed 200 p.p.m. PAM solutions at $Re_\tau = 139$. The convergence of the mean
 165 velocities is achieved, and the long-time averages, $\langle U_s \rangle_{N_t}$, fall into the reliability margin
 166 of $\pm 2 \sigma_{u_s} / \langle U_s \rangle$ [1]. Here, a representative value of $\sigma_{u_s} = 0.1 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ was used in figure 6.
 167 Even though, compared to the convergence profiles of the water flow, shown in figure 4, the
 168 oscillations of the PAM profiles are more significant, even in the last 20% of the data. The
 169 interaction of polymer molecules with the turbulent water flow in PAM solutions, which
 170 enhances the wall-parallel velocity fluctuations, might be the reason.

Figure 5. Statistical convergence of (a) $\langle u_s \rangle$, (b) $\langle u_s u_n \rangle$, (c) $\langle u_s^2 \rangle$, and (d) $\langle u_n^2 \rangle$ at four different wall distances. Here, N is the number of samples. Each profile is normalized by its corresponding long-time average. The results correspond to the fully-developed water flow at $Re_\tau = 200$.

Figure 6. Variation of the ensemble-averaged streamwise velocity, $\langle U_s \rangle_N$, at four different wall distances, as a function of the sample number N for 200 p.p.m. fully-developed PAM solution flow at $Re_\tau = 139$. The long-time average $\langle U_s \rangle_{N_t}$ normalizes the result, where $N_t = 11\,000$, is the total number of the velocity fields. The dashed black lines denote the reliability margins [1].

171 The top row of figure 7(a-b) illustrates the fast convergence of the first-order averages
 172 of velocity fluctuations, $\langle u_s \rangle_{N_t} \rightarrow 0$, at the probed locations from the buffer to the outer
 173 layer near the centerline for both 200 p.p.m. and 400 p.p.m. C-FPG PAM solutions at
 174 $Re_\tau = 139$. Similar fast convergences were observed for other tested flow conditions but are
 175 not presented here for the brevity of the discussion. The mean wall-parallel and wall-normal
 176 Reynolds stresses demonstrate excellent convergence with $\approx 80\%$ of samples. Nevertheless,
 177 these Reynolds stresses converge faster in the 200 p.p.m. than in the 400 p.p.m. solution.

Figure 7. Statistical convergence of $\langle u_s \rangle$, $\langle u_s u_n \rangle$ and $\langle u_s^2 \rangle$ at four different wall distances for (a) 200 p.p.m. and (b) 400 p.p.m. C-FPG full-developed PAM solution flows at $Re_\tau = 139$. Here, $N_t = 11\,000$ and each profile is normalized by its corresponding long-time average.

178 Compared to water, PAM solutions demonstrate a slower convergence for a similar num-

Table III. Random noises of the mean wall-parallel velocity and Reynolds stresses at different wall-normal positions for the C-FPG 200 p.p.m. PAM solution flow at three different Re_τ (see table II).

Parameter	$Re_\tau = 122$			$Re_\tau = 139$			$Re_\tau = 154$		
	$n^+ = 14$	50	100	$n^+ = 17$	50	100	$n^+ = 19$	55	100
$e_{R,\langle U_s \rangle} \%$	1.07	0.60	0.40	0.63	0.51	0.30	1.66	1.24	0.87
$e_{R,\langle u_s u_n \rangle} \%$	6.81	9.47	7.52	10.09	6.83	10.07	7.67	10.41	10.89
$e_{R,\langle u_s^2 \rangle} \%$	3.43	3.77	6.23	2.95	2.34	2.03	1.92	2.75	2.47
$e_{R,\langle u_n^2 \rangle} \%$	2.53	1.82	1.96	2.16	3.46	1.61	4.96	2.92	1.71

ber of samples. As figure 7(a,b) illustrates, the amplitude of the mean Reynolds shear stresses greatly oscillate in the first 20 – 30 % of the data, and they hardly converge until ≈ 90 % of the samples were used for averaging. This behavior is evident for both tested PAM solutions, and the oscillations are more violent than their counterpart for the water flow.

The random noises of the mean velocity measurements are listed in table III and table IV for 200 p.p.m. and 400 p.p.m. fully-developed C-FPG PAM solution flows. The maximum calculated $e_{R,\langle U_s \rangle}$ for the 200 p.p.m. flow is $\approx 1.66\%$ for $n^+ \approx 19$ at $Re_\tau = 154$ and it is $\approx 1.37\%$ for $n^+ \approx 16$ at $Re_\tau = 141$ for the 400 p.p.m. flow. The results show that the random noises reduce for wall positions farther from the wall and tend to $e_{R,\langle U_s \rangle} < 1$ %. As discussed before, compared to the pure water flow, the random noises of mean velocities are an order of magnitude larger in the tested PAM solutions due to the enhancement of longitudinal velocity fluctuations. Overall, the wall-parallel Reynolds stresses show a maximum random noise lower than ≈ 6.5 % in the 200 p.p.m. and ≈ 4.5 % in the 400 p.p.m. solutions. The random noise of $\langle u_n^2 \rangle$ Reynolds stress measurements does not exceed ≈ 5.0 % in the 200 p.p.m. and ≈ 3.5 % in the 400 p.p.m. solutions.

As figure 7(a,b) demonstrates, the random noises of $\langle u_s u_n \rangle$ measurement, listed in table III and table IV, are relatively higher compared to the mean wall-parallel and -normal Reynolds stresses in the polymer solutions. Overall, $e_{R,\langle u_s u_n \rangle} < 11$ % in the monitored wall-normal positions in the 200 p.p.m. and $e_{R,\langle u_s u_n \rangle} < 20$ % in the 400 p.p.m. solution. This relatively large random noise is associated with high amplitude fluctuations near the wall region. Overall, the random noises of mean Reynolds shear stress measurements in the tested

Table IV. Random noises of the mean wall-parallel velocity and Reynolds stresses at different wall-normal positions for the C-FPG 400 p.p.m. PAM solution flow at three different Re_τ (see table II).

Parameter	$Re_\tau = 108$			$Re_\tau = 124$			$Re_\tau = 141$		
	$n^+ = 12$	43	79	$n^+ = 16$	52	96	$n^+ = 16$	57	89
$e_{R,\langle U_s \rangle} \%$	1.27	0.90	1.06	1.91	1.13	0.55	1.37	0.83	0.82
$e_{R,\langle u_s u_n \rangle} \%$	6.93	9.34	12.58	19.34	9.07	6.99	11.93	7.42	12.48
$e_{R,\langle u_s^2 \rangle} \%$	4.21	4.11	3.11	3.76	2.12	2.70	2.85	2.46	4.44
$e_{R,\langle u_n^2 \rangle} \%$	2.59	2.06	3.53	1.83	1.48	1.70	2.01	3.31	2.65

201 polymer solutions are $\times 2 - 3$ more intense than the fully-developed water flow.

202 III. GENERALISED VELOCITY APPROACH

203 Across a channel with nonuniform curved walls, the edge velocity U_e is not necessarily
 204 constant. A more realistic way of calculating integral quantities, as proposed by Spalart and
 205 Watmuff [5], is by defining a generalised velocity as:

$$\langle \tilde{U} \rangle(s, n) = - \int_0^n \langle \omega_z \rangle(s, n') dn', \quad (9)$$

206 where, $\langle \omega_z \rangle(s, n)$ is the mean spanwise vorticity component. Here, $\langle \omega_z \rangle$ can be calculated
 207 using the mean wall-parallel and -normal components of velocity as:

$$\langle \omega_z \rangle = \frac{\partial \langle U_n \rangle}{\partial s} - \frac{\partial \langle U_s \rangle}{\partial n}. \quad (10)$$

208 Using equation 9, \tilde{U}_e is:

$$\tilde{U}_e(s) = - \int_0^\infty \langle \omega_z \rangle(s, n) dn. \quad (11)$$

209 Accordingly, the generalised integral quantities are defined as:

$$\tilde{\delta}^*(s) = - \frac{1}{\tilde{U}_e(s)} \int_0^\infty n \langle \omega_z \rangle dn, \quad (12)$$

$$\tilde{\delta}^*(s) = - \frac{2}{\tilde{U}_e^2(s)} \int_0^\infty n \langle \tilde{U} \rangle \langle \omega_z \rangle dn - \tilde{\delta}^*(s). \quad (13)$$

210 This method was utilised by Balin and Jansen [6] and Coleman et al. [7], among others,
 211 for the DNS of turbulent flows over bumps, where the computed velocity fields had a high

212 spatial resolution, and it was straightforward to calculate high-accuracy vorticity fields.
 213 However, experimentally obtained velocity fields, even the ones from PIV, lack sufficient
 214 resolution and make it challenging to use the generalised velocity approach to evaluate the
 215 integral quantities. This issue was also noted by Maciel et al. [8].

216 IV. DIMENSIONAL REYNOLDS SHEAR STRESS

217 Dimensional Reynolds shear stress profiles at chosen streamwise positions are illustrated
 218 in figure 8(a-c). Refer to the data provided in the Supplementary Material for other dimen-
 219 sional and outer-normalised profiles.

Figure 8. Wall-normal variations of the dimensional mean Reynolds shear stress profiles at eight selected wall-parallel positions for accelerating (a) water, (b) 200 p.p.m., and (c) 400 p.p.m. flows over the flat surface of the channel’s convergence region.

220 **V. ORDER-OF-MAGNITUDE CALCULATION OF PAKDEL-MCKINLEY CRI-**
221 **TERION**

222 To demonstrate that the flow is influenced by elastic hoop stresses, we calculate the
223 stability parameter M at the highest flow rate for the 400 p.p.m. PAM solution. Relaxation
224 time $t_{\max} = 286.66$ ms, local shear rate $\dot{\gamma}_w \approx 1.88 \times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$, boundary layer thickness
225 $\delta \approx 0.5h_{\text{in}} = 4$ mm, radius of curvature $r_c = 1$ mm (at the bump fillets), yields a Weissenberg
226 Number Wi of

$$Wi = t_{\max} \times \dot{\gamma}_w \approx 0.287 \text{ s} \times 1880 \text{ s}^{-1} \approx 540.$$

227 The Pakdel-McKinley criterion (M) uses the ratio of the characteristic length scale (BL
228 thickness) to the curvature radius [9]:

$$M = \sqrt{\frac{\delta}{r_c} Wi} = \sqrt{\frac{4 \text{ mm}}{1 \text{ mm}} \times 540} = \sqrt{2160} \approx 46.5$$

229 Since $M \approx 46.5$ is significantly greater than the typical critical threshold ($M_{\text{crit}} \approx 6$)
230 reported in literature for similar geometries, the flow is in a regime where purely elastic
231 instabilities and hoop stresses are dominant. This physically explains why the flow does
232 not return to a Newtonian "laminar" state despite the strong favourable pressure gradient;
233 instead, the curvature maintains high elastic activity, resulting in the elevated $\langle u_s^2 \rangle^+$ values
234 and the absence of a standard log-law.

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